

Atmospheric Aerosol Spatial Variability: Impacts on Air Quality and Climate Change

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SUMMARY

Atmospheric aerosols cause millions of excess deaths per year globally and play a significant role in the climate change problem. Fine and coarse aerosols arise from both natural sources and anthropogenic activities and can be either directly emitted or formed in the atmosphere. Since neither the sources of aerosols nor their secondary formation are distributed evenly around the globe, their concentrations, composition, and characteristics exhibit significant spatial variability. Understanding this spatial variability is essential for deploying successful mitigation strategies that will improve air quality and help minimize climate change. This review summarizes our current understanding and corresponding knowledge gaps regarding the variability of aerosol mass and number concentrations at different scales. Improving existing modeling tools can reduce the uncertainty regarding the magnitude of the effects of aerosols, while remote sensing, low-cost sensors, and international collaboration can bridge the measurement gaps in developing countries and remote areas.

KEYWORDS

Aerosols, Spatial variability, Air quality, Human Health, Ecosystems

INTRODUCTION

Atmospheric aerosols or particulate matter (PM) cover a wide range of sizes starting from stable clusters consisting of a few molecules with sizes around 1 nm and extending up to 100 μm (Figure 1). Most of them are smaller than 100 nm and are in the ultrafine particle (UFP) range. However, these smallest particles have low mass concentrations. Most of the particle mass is found in two modes, the accumulation mode (0.1 to 2.5 μm) and the coarse mode (above 2.5 μm). Particle number and mass concentrations have often very different behavior in the atmosphere because they are influenced by different processes¹. The particle number concentration is influenced or even dominated by homogeneous nucleation², but nucleation forms negligible PM mass. Coagulation is the most important sink of the smallest particles reducing dramatically the high particle number concentrations. However, coagulation conserves mass. Finally, condensation is the most important process for the production of secondary particle mass, but it conserves particle number.

Most of the particles contain a variety of inorganic and organic chemical compounds. The most important inorganic constituents of atmospheric PM are sulfates, nitrates, chloride, ammonium, water and a variety of metals and their oxides. Tens of thousands of organic compounds can be found in atmospheric PM covering practically every chemical family (alkanes, aromatics, acids, aldehydes, ketones, hyperoxides, organonitrates, multifunctional compounds). The sources of atmospheric PM are both anthropogenic (combustion of fossil fuels, cooking, industrial processes, wood burning, etc.) and natural (emissions of vegetation, oceans, etc.).

44 For centuries it has been assumed that atmospheric PM is emitted from sources, is nonvolatile and inert and is
45 transported in the atmosphere with the winds and is eventually removed. It is now clear that especially the fine PM
46 ($PM_{2.5}$) is produced by gas-to-particle conversion processes. Pollutants emitted as vapors (SO_2 , NO and NO_2 , NH_3 ,
47 volatile organic compounds, etc.) react in the gas phase producing compounds with low volatility which are then
48 transferred to the particle phase forming secondary PM. Primary particles are also often semivolatile, evaporate
49 partially after emission, and the resulting vapors can then react in the atmosphere forming secondary aerosol.

50 Both aerosol number and mass exhibit significant variability in space. This variability is characterized by distinct
51 scales. Aerosol concentrations vary by more than an order of magnitude next to a point source (tailpipe, stack,
52 chimney, etc.) due to their rapid mixing and dilution with the ambient air³. The characteristic length scale is of the
53 order of meters. This is quite important for the exposure of drivers on a major road or pedestrians walking next to
54 heavy traffic⁴. Then there is a second scale of tens or hundreds of meters as the corresponding emissions are further
55 mixed with the ambient air. The next scale is the urban scale, of the order of 1 km in which different neighborhoods
56 in a city are characterized by different aerosol levels^{5,6,7}. Recent advances in high-resolution satellite observations and
57 low-cost sensor networks have improved our ability to map intra-city air pollution, revealing spatial disparities in
58 aerosol levels that correspond to socioeconomic and land-use patterns⁸. PM levels vary between cities and their
59 surroundings at a scale of tens of kilometers^{9,10,11,12}, and then there is the regional variation at hundreds of
60 kilometers^{10,11}. Aerosol spatial variability is directly connected with its temporal variability via the wind speed¹³. In
61 general, the spatial variability of PM decreases gradually with distance from its source in the downwind direction.
62 High aerosol temporal variability and low wind speed correspond to high aerosol spatial variability. At the same time
63 there is variation with altitude with aerosol concentrations tending to decrease with height¹⁴. However, there are often
64 plumes with high aerosol levels (usually due to a major fire or a dust episode) with locally elevated concentrations
65 high above the ground¹⁵. These plumes can be transported over large distances, of the order of hundreds or even
66 thousands of kilometers^{16,17}.

67 Globally, exposure to ambient PM is estimated to lead to 7.5-10.3 million premature deaths globally per year¹⁸. PM
68 is ranked as the fifth greatest risk factor for mortality in the Global Burden of Disease, Injuries, and Risk Factors
69 Study¹⁹. These effects have been mainly associated with fine PM ($PM_{2.5}$) mass concentration. There have been tens of
70 studies around the world attempting to link the contribution of different sources and/or concentrations of PM
71 components to mortality, but the results have been quite inconsistent^{20,21}. There is significant evidence in the health
72 literature suggesting that nanoparticles may be the most dangerous part of PM²². However, the association between
73 exposure to nanoparticles and health damages is inconsistent^{20,21}. Therefore, $PM_{2.5}$ remains the major regulatory target
74 for the reduction of the health effects of atmospheric aerosols²³. PM variability at the surface where human live is
75 clearly the most important concern.

76 At the same time, atmospheric aerosol particles influence the Earth's radiation balance directly by scattering and
77 absorbing radiation, and indirectly by affecting the reflectivity and lifetime of clouds. The role of these particles in
78 the energy balance of our planet, regarding both short and long wave radiation, is one of the major uncertainties in the
79 problem of climate change²⁴. The direct effect is mainly driven by the fine PM mass. However, the PM concentrations
80 aloft and the vertical variability are quite important. The indirect effect of PM is mainly related to a subset of particles
81 that can act as cloud condensation nuclei (CCN) or ice nuclei (IN). In this case particle number concentration comes
82 to the forefront. CCN are larger particles (often the concentration of particles larger than 100 nm, N_{100} , or 50 nm, N_{50} ,
83 is used as a rough metric of CCN levels) that can become cloud droplets and lead to the formation of a cloud in a
84 cooling air mass. The IN are also relatively large particles, but they have the spatial ability to serve as the nucleus for
85 the formation of an ice crystal. This requires quite spatial morphology of the particle, and IN are quite rare particles.

86 The removal of atmospheric particles by dry (without the involvement of rain or snow) and wet (rain, snow) deposition
87 is also a significant factor determining their spatial and temporal variability. The removed particles are deposited on
88 a variety of ecosystems including oceans, forests, crops, etc., and interact with them. The interactions can be positive
89 for the ecosystems with the addition of valuable nutrients or highly detrimental (acidification, addition of harmful
90 metals, etc.)²⁵.

91 The impacts of particulate matter on human health, ecosystems, and climate depend on its concentration, size
92 distribution, and composition. Developing successful mitigation strategies requires quantifying the variability of
93 aerosols in space and time. Unfortunately, this is extremely challenging as particulate matter exhibits different scales
94 of variability in space, in size (it covers 6 orders of magnitude in diameter) and in composition. Additional challenges
95 arise due to the availability of measurements and the existing knowledge gaps that prevent accurate model predictions.
96 To successfully improve air quality and combat climate change, it is important to understand the factors that drive
97 aerosol variability and how this variability is manifested in different environments. In this paper we review the
98 considerable progress that has been made during the last few decades in the quantification of this variability and
99 discuss the major remaining challenges.

100 In the next paragraphs we summarize the sources of aerosols, their scales of variation and their magnitude in different
101 environments, the differences in variation of particle mass, number and particle type and their interactions with
102 environmental factors that help create this variability. This information is synthesized and is linked to their health
103 effects, effects on climate and ecosystems. Finally, next steps for the research and the policy community are proposed.

104 **SYNTHESIS**

105 *Sources of aerosols*

106 Atmospheric particulate matter is either directly emitted from natural and anthropogenic sources or formed in the
107 atmosphere through gas-to-particle formation processes (condensation on pre-existing particles and new particle
108 formation). Different sources emit or contribute to the formation of secondary aerosols with different chemical
109 characteristics and at different rates; therefore, the first factor that influences the variability of atmospheric particles
110 is the variability of their sources. This section identifies the various aerosol sources and briefly describes the typical
111 chemical characteristics of the corresponding particles originating from each source.

112 **Natural:** Natural sources of PM including soil, deserts, oceans, vegetation, volcanic eruptions, and wildfires contribute
113 approximately 90% of the global aerosol emissions (Table 1). Most of the natural primary aerosols are generated from
114 the interaction of the wind with the surface of our planet and the corresponding emissions are therefore sensitive to
115 meteorology and climate. Primary inorganic aerosol emitted from natural sources consists of mineral compounds
116 (quartz, calcite, dolomite, etc.) produced from windblown dust and sea salt²⁶. In some regions, organic compounds are
117 the main components of natural aerosols. Over pristine tropical forests, primary biogenic aerosols, such as fungal spores,
118 can account for up to 45% of the coarse aerosol mass²⁹. Natural primary aerosols are more prominent in coarse mode,
119 although they can also contribute to the fine particles. For example, over the oceans during bloom phytoplankton
120 periods, the contribution of organic compounds to the submicron sea salt aerosol can reach up to 63%³⁰.

121 **Anthropogenic:** Even though the global emissions of anthropogenic aerosols are lower compared to natural sources
122 (Table 1), in urban and industrial areas, which are the most populated areas, human activities are the dominant source
123 of PM. These anthropogenic particles remain in the atmosphere for weeks and reach even the most pristine regions of
124 our planet³¹.

125 The combustion of fossil fuels for transportation (vehicles, ships, trains, planes), power generation, and heating
126 purposes, is a significant source of black carbon (BC), organic aerosol (OA), secondary precursors, trace elements
127 (Fe, Zn, Ni, etc.), and heavy metals (Pb, As, Cd, Cr, etc.)¹. Another important source of organic aerosol is biomass
128 burning, which includes the combustion of biomass (wood, shrubs, and peat) for heating and cooking purposes as well
129 as prescribed burning during agricultural activities. In certain areas, the role of uncontrolled industrial emissions can
130 be significant. While mineral dust predominantly originates from natural sources, it is also emitted by various
131 anthropogenic activities (roadways, mining, agriculture, livestock herding, etc.)³². Other notable sources include
132 cooking³³ and the use of consumer products³⁴.

133 **Secondary aerosol production:** The atmosphere itself is one of the most important sources of PM, as homogeneous
134 and heterogeneous atmospheric reactions can form secondary aerosol. Secondary aerosol formation depends on
135 multiple factors including the availability of precursors and atmospheric oxidants and meteorological conditions (solar
136 radiation, relative humidity, cloud presence and cloud liquid water content).

137 The primary components of secondary inorganic aerosol are sulfates and nitrates. Sulfate is the oxidation product of
138 sulfur dioxide, which is emitted predominantly from fossil fuel combustion, and dimethyl sulfide (DMS), which is
139 emitted from phytoplankton²⁶. The precursors of nitrates are nitrogen oxides (NO_x), which react in the atmosphere
140 and produce nitric acid (HNO₃). In turn, HNO₃ reacts with ammonia or other alkaline aerosol components (CaCO₃,
141 NaCl, etc.) and forms particulate nitrates. Both anthropogenic and biogenic sources emit thousands of volatile and
142 semi-volatile organic compounds (VOCs and SVOCs). The oxidation reactions of larger organic compounds (more
143 than 5 carbon atoms) form, together with other products, secondary organic aerosol (SOA), that is often the dominant
144 component of OA³⁵.

145 The physicochemical characteristics of particles change as secondary material condenses on them or as they coagulate
146 with other particles. Therefore, the aerosols that humans breathe, even if they came from a specific source, can be
147 physically, chemically and toxicologically different from their original form³⁶.

148 **New particle formation:** Atmospheric new particle formation (NPF) is the most important source of particle number
149 in the atmosphere. NPF occurs in two steps: the initial formation and stabilization of small (<2 nm) molecular clusters
150 from various gaseous precursors, and their subsequent growth. The formation of new particles is largely driven by the
151 availability of condensable vapors and favorable conditions (high solar radiation, low concentration of preexisting
152 particles, etc.)³⁷. NPF has been observed worldwide in all types of environments, from pristine forests and high-
153 elevation sites to polluted megacities, coastal regions and the Arctic^{37,38}.

154 Sulfuric acid appears to be the single most important precursor for atmospheric NPF due to its prevalence in the
155 atmosphere and its extremely low volatility in the presence of water vapor³⁹. However, sulfuric acid-water nucleation
156 is a relatively slow process in the lower troposphere. Ammonia, amines, low volatility organic compounds, various
157 inorganic molecules and atmospheric ions, all act synergistically with sulfuric acid leading to NPF⁴⁰.

158 ***PM variability and atmospheric processes***

159 After their entrance in the atmosphere, emission, particles evolve continuously due to a series of physicochemical
160 processes that can increase or decrease their concentrations and alter their chemical and physical characteristics. This
161 section describes these processes as well as their characteristic length scales.

162 **Variation around sources:** The concentration of primary particles decreases rapidly with distance from their sources
163 due to dispersion and dilution. Particles related to traffic decrease dramatically 100-400 m away from busy roads³.
164 Similarly, industrial primary PM emissions have usually a significantly reduced impact at distances more than 1 km
165 from the facility⁴¹.

166 Even if their concentration decreases, atmospheric particles can travel substantial distances (sometimes even
167 thousands of kilometers) depending on particle type, size, and meteorological conditions⁴². Key factors like altitude
168 of emission, wet deposition, vertical mixing, and wind speed significantly influence how far particles can travel.
169 Additionally, topography plays a crucial role, as mountains and valleys can trap pollutants in specific regions.

170 Evaporation of semi-volatile organic material also increases the concentration gradient around combustion sources⁴³.
171 This evaporation accelerates as the particles get diluted. As a result, primary OA levels can drop to close to zero a few
172 hundred kilometers away from their sources⁴⁴. Modeling studies indicate that the average transport distance for
173 primary fine PM components is around 100-200 km, while secondary PM species, such as sulfate and SOA, travel
174 greater distances, with an average transport distance of over 350 km⁴².

175 Aerosol number decreases more rapidly around a combustion source than the corresponding fine aerosol mass. This
176 is mainly due to coagulation that is quite rapid in the high concentration region close to a source. Zhu et al.⁴⁵ found
177 that at 300 m away from a major highway the particle number returned to its background levels.

178 Nucleation inside a fresh pollution plume can increase particle number downwind of the source. High number
179 concentrations of secondary particles have been reported, for example inside wildfire plumes⁴⁶ and industrial plumes⁴⁷.
180 This can lead to different number concentration patterns compared to mass.

181 **Secondary formation and corresponding length scales:** SOA forms within hours after the emissions of the VOC
182 precursors in the atmosphere. Most of the SOA mass is formed within a distance of 100-150 km from the source of
183 VOC precursors⁴⁸, while significant formation continues up to 500-600 km away^{49,50}. Sulfate formation is a relatively
184 slow process extending over hundreds of kilometers while that of ammonium nitrate is rather localized, with
185 concentrations decreasing significantly after 50 km⁵⁰.

186 Multiple processes can influence the characteristic time and length scales of secondary formation. For example,
187 multiphase chemistry, which promotes secondary aerosol formation, is more prominent during severe localized haze
188 events^{51,52}. On the other hand, the photochemistry occurring inside biomass burning and wildfire plumes can increase
189 significantly SOA concentrations and affect areas hundreds of kilometers away from the source⁵³. The processes and
190 the mechanisms of biomass burning SOA production and their corresponding contributions to regional pollution far
191 from the fires remain an area of active research.

192 NPF events often occur on a regional scale (100-1000 km) and most previous studies have focused on these types of
193 events^{37,54}. Large scale (reaching 600 km) NPF events have been observed in the remote marine boundary layer⁵⁵,
194 however they appear to be less frequent and to be limited by the availability of gas-phase bases like ammonia and
195 amines. Local NPF events (scale of meters to a few kilometers) can also occur and they have been observed in
196 industrial⁵⁶ and wildfire⁴⁶ plumes, agricultural areas⁵⁷ and others⁵⁸. The current methods and tools utilized for studying
197 local NPF events remain limited⁵⁹.

198 **Sinks of atmospheric aerosol:** Most atmospheric PM ends its lifecycle through deposition on the surface of our planet.
199 Dry deposition leads to the removal of particles on surfaces via gravitational settling and/or Brownian diffusion; while
200 wet deposition is the removal by precipitation (rain, snow, hail)¹. The positive (addition of nutrients to ecosystems) or
201 negative (deposition of toxics or acid deposition) effects of deposition will be discussed in a subsequent section.

202 The rate of dry deposition of particles depends dramatically on their size, with larger particles depositing faster than
203 smaller ones. The dry deposition of semi-volatile species also reduces indirectly the concentrations of particles⁶⁰. For
204 example, nitric acid, which is quite soluble in water, deposits rapidly on surfaces. This causes ammonium nitrate to
205 evaporate from the particulate to the gas-phase to restore equilibrium between the two phases.

206 For most aerosols, wet deposition is the most efficient atmospheric sink. The distinct rainfall patterns affect the
207 temporal variation of aerosols, which can be reflected as spatial variation if one examines a snapshot in time. At longer
208 timescales (months, seasons, or annually), these gradients are smoothed out, and their scale is determined by the
209 regional average rainfall. Rain removes larger particles from the atmosphere more efficiently than smaller ones. Wet
210 regions have thus both lower emissions and faster removal of coarse particles, leading to relatively lower
211 concentrations⁶¹. Accurately constraining the wet deposition parameters in models is necessary to improve predictions,
212 especially in severely polluted areas and during haze events⁶².

213 Additional removal mechanisms include the evaporation of semi-volatile components from particles, which affects
214 the particle mass, and coagulation, which is a major removal mechanism of particle number. Particles evaporate
215 partially as they disperse and dilute in the atmosphere, or as atmospheric temperature increases. Coagulation removes
216 primarily the smallest atmospheric particles (few nm) as they collide with larger particles in a matter of hours.

217 **Variation of PM mass concentration in different environments**

218 The driving forces (sources and atmospheric processes) vary in different environments and therefore result in the
219 variability of aerosol levels and properties in the corresponding areas. In this section, we examine the spatial variability
220 of fine particle mass (PM_{2.5}) concentrations near the ground level in an urban, regional and global scale, the variability
221 of coarse particles and the vertical variability of both fine and coarse PM. Understanding the variability of PM_{2.5} near
222 the surface, where human reside, is especially important as the mass of fine PM is the primary regulatory objective
223 for mitigating the health impacts of atmospheric aerosols²³.

224 **Urban environment:** Fine PM in urban areas originates from both local and regional sources (through long-range
225 transport). In heavily polluted cities, local sources typically dominate; however, when local emissions are regulated,

226 the relative importance of long-range transport increases. Since the contribution of long-range transport tends to be
227 relatively uniform across an urban area, spatial gradients within the city are primarily due to the variability of local
228 sources, such as industry, biomass burning, transportation, and cooking^{7,63}. As an example of aerosol average spatial
229 variability in an urban environment, Figure 2 illustrates the average spatial distribution of source contributions in
230 Athens, Greece.

231 Different aerosol components have different dominant sources and therefore different distributions in space⁶⁴. For
232 primary components like primary OA and BC, local sources are important and therefore significant gradients are
233 present near their sources. For example, for local traffic-related PM_{2.5} including BC, a travel distance of 100-400 m
234 has been reported³. In contrast, slow forming secondary components like sulfate have smaller gradients⁷.

235 Regulatory PM_{2.5} monitoring networks inside cities are sparse and cannot capture the corresponding variability.
236 Networks of low cost PM_{2.5} sensors⁶⁴ are a promising tool for this task, but a number of challenges need to be
237 overcome⁶⁵.

238 PM_{2.5} from urban areas is transported downwind affecting surrounding regions. The influence of pollutants emitted in
239 Paris has been observed up to 50 km from the city center⁹.

240 **Continental:** The variation of PM levels over continents depends on the spatial variation of sources, topography, and
241 meteorological conditions (Figure 3). The PM_{2.5} concentrations are higher close to their sources, but due to secondary
242 aerosol formation they can impact areas hundreds of km away from their origin.

243 Satellite measurements of the aerosol optical depth (AOD) provide valuable information about the regional PM spatial
244 variability^{68,69}. For example, in Europe (Figure 4), AOD increases from north to south because of higher secondary
245 aerosol formation rates and higher dust levels in the south¹². High AOD values are observed over large urban areas
246 and polluted regions like the Po Valley in Italy¹² and the valleys of California in eastern US¹⁴. In western US, high
247 local AOD is associated with high dust levels⁶⁹. High values of AOD (above 1) are reported in parts of China, India
248 and elsewhere in Asia (e.g., central Laos, northern Thailand and northern Vietnam) over hundreds of km indicating
249 the corresponding high PM values^{14,70}.

250 **Global:** The spatial variation of fine PM on a global scale is determined by its lifetime which is of the order of week
251 on average⁷¹. Annual multi-model median near-surface distributions of fine PM chemical composition show largest
252 mass concentrations over the continents for anthropogenic aerosol components like sulfate, organics and black carbon
253 and almost an order of magnitude lower levels over the ocean (Figure 5). The opposite applies to sea-spray which
254 although it is mostly emitted in the coarse mode has also a submicron mode that maximizes as expected over the
255 oceans. Submicron dust aerosol peaks over land but has significant levels at the outflow of desert areas⁷².

256 **Vertical variation:** Aerosols and their precursors are mainly emitted near-surface, although emissions from wildfires,
257 aircraft, and volcanoes can reach several kilometers above ground⁷³. Elevated levels of OA and BC have been often
258 observed at altitudes 2-6 km^{74,75} usually associated with biomass burning plumes. The vertical distribution of
259 secondary aerosols is affected by temperature, with the partitioning of their semi-volatile components favoring the
260 particulate phase with decreasing temperature⁷⁶. Aircraft campaigns over the Amazon forest have shown high aerosol
261 (sulfate, black carbon, ammonium and organics) concentrations above ground up to 4 km altitude and at 10-14 km
262 altitude (contributed by nitrate and secondary biogenic organics)⁷⁷ (Figure 6).

263 **Coarse particles:** The resuspension of dust from roads is the dominant anthropogenic source of coarse aerosols,
264 accounting for approximately 90% of coarse PM emissions in urban environments⁴. Other anthropogenic sources that
265 contribute to coarse aerosol levels, albeit to a lesser extent, include emissions from industrial activities, combustion
266 (e.g., from vehicles and power plants), and agricultural practices. The spatial variability of coarse particles (PM₁₀) in
267 urban areas is generally higher than that of fine particles (PM_{2.5}) due to differences in their sources and transport
268 mechanisms⁷⁸. This is also true in other scales and areas¹⁰. Urban areas generally demonstrate higher concentrations
269 attributable to localized emissions in contrast to rural ones⁷⁹.

270 Sea-spray emissions are mostly (60% of emitted mass) coarse particles and have a short residence time in the
271 atmosphere estimated at 0.5 d¹². Thus, sea salt aerosols significantly contribute to aerosol mass and number near their
272 sources and especially in coastal areas⁸⁰.

273 Wind-driven erosion of soils is a primary contributor to coarse particulate matter, particularly in arid and semi-arid
274 regions from where dust can be transported over long distances due to its relatively long residence time of about 4 d⁷¹.
275 Desert dust mass concentrations span more than 4 orders of magnitude from a few mg m⁻³ over source regions to less
276 than 1 µg m⁻³ in remote locations¹⁷. During dust outbreaks, hourly PM₁₀ levels above 1000 µg m⁻³ have been recorded
277 in cities like Sydney⁸¹ and Heraklion⁸². In such cases dust is transported through the middle troposphere and reaches
278 the surface through sedimentation and dispersion⁸³.

279 Primary biological material (bacteria, viruses, fungal spores, and fragments of living organisms including pollen) can
280 be a significant fraction of coarse PM⁸⁴. The number concentrations of bioaerosols varies spatially from a few cells
281 m⁻³ to 10⁶ cells m⁻³⁸⁵.

282 *Variation in aerosol number concentration*

283 The variability of particle number concentrations is often quite different from that of the corresponding mass
284 concentrations. In this section, we examine the variation of aerosol number concentrations in different scales. We also
285 discuss the spatial distribution of particles that function as cloud condensation nuclei (CCN) and ice nuclei (IN). Both
286 CNN and IN play a key role in the meteorology and climate of our planet.

287 **Urban areas:** Primary particle emissions can be the dominant source of particle number within urban areas⁷⁹. Areas
288 with dense traffic sites are characterized by the highest particle number concentrations⁸⁶. High particle number levels
289 are also observed near airports and restaurants leading to significant spatial concentration gradients at distances of a
290 few hundred meters⁶. Cyrus et al.⁸⁷ found that the number concentration near traffic sites were on average 1.2 to 1.8
291 times higher than the urban background. Saha et al.⁸⁸ estimated that the spatial heterogeneity of particle number was
292 up to 3 times higher than that of PM_{2.5} mass in Pittsburgh, US. High variabilities in particle number, reaching even an
293 order of magnitude, have been observed in cities globally^{89,90}.

294 Land-use regression models combined with particle number measurements in multiple locations can give valuable
295 insights into the spatial variability inside and outside of urban areas. Saha et al.¹¹ estimated that in urban areas in the
296 U.S the average number concentrations of particles with diameters less than 10 nm is about 3 times higher than in the
297 corresponding rural areas. They concluded that the particle number concentration inside a city was approximately 2-
298 4 times higher than the corresponding levels of the city's metropolitan area (15-50 km away from the city center).
299 Conversely, the measured PM_{2.5} levels in suburban and rural areas were comparable to the city center. Similar spatial
300 gradients of particle number between in-city and near-city areas have been observed in Augsburg, Germany⁹¹ and in
301 Shanghai, China⁹².

302 **Continental:** Significant variation in particle number concentration is also observed on continental scales. Generally,
303 the number concentrations are higher near NPF regions or areas with high localized primary emissions, including
304 urban⁹³ and industrial areas⁴⁷. Typically, the concentrations decrease to background levels a few tens of kilometers
305 from these hotspots. However, for large metropolitan areas, the number concentrations can be affected even 200 km
306 downwind⁹⁴. Remote continental sites can be influenced by regional NPF events³⁷ that can double (or even triple) the
307 existing concentrations⁹⁵.

308 Some regions around the world display characteristic spatial variability. For example, in Europe, southern and central
309 regions display higher number concentrations compared to northern regions⁹⁶. Very small particles with diameter less
310 than 10 nm exhibit higher spatial variability than larger ones (diameters between 10 and 100 nm)⁹⁷.

311 **Global:** Based on the existing measurements the average N_{10} (particles with diameter higher than 10 nm) levels range
312 from 10² cm⁻³ in polar sites to 10⁵ cm⁻³ in urban sites⁹⁸. It is estimated that 70-90% of the total particle number
313 originates from NPF over tropical and mid-latitude oceans⁴⁰ while this range is more variable (35-95%) over
314 continental and more polluted areas, where primary emissions become more important^{40,97}. Analyzing measurements

315 from 36 sites, Nieminen et al.³⁸ found that NPF rates were 1-2 orders of magnitude higher in anthropogenically
316 dominated continental areas than more pristine ones. This can partially explain (together with primary number
317 emissions) the significant spatial differences observed in particle number on a global scale. Overall, the concentrations
318 predicted by global models are in good agreement with ground-based measurements². Annual multi-model median of
319 N_3 number concentrations (diameter more than 3 nm) near-surface over continental regions vary between 1000 and
320 10,000 cm^{-3} , while over the marine boundary layer (MBL) they are at least one order of magnitude lower varying
321 between 100 and 2000 cm^{-3} , rarely exceeding 300 cm^{-3} (Figure 8)⁷².

322 **Vertical variation of particle number:** Particle number concentrations are usually much higher near the ground
323 compared to higher altitudes. Elevated particle number concentration can be observed at higher altitudes if an emission
324 source is located there. Tall industrial chimneys⁴⁷, volcanoes⁹⁹, aviation¹⁰⁰, and wildfires¹⁶ can notably increase the
325 particle number concentrations at higher altitudes. At these levels the particles have longer lifetimes (they are often
326 above the raining clouds) and can travel longer distances³⁷.

327 NPF takes place at all altitudes¹⁰¹. Some studies¹⁰² have reported higher number concentrations due to NPF at the
328 ground level, while others¹⁰³ have found that NPF can take place at higher altitude creating local concentration
329 maxima. The corresponding formed particles can be later transported upwards¹⁰² or downwards¹⁰³, depending on
330 where they are formed, and can grow to larger sizes.

331 **Cloud condensation nuclei:** Cloud condensation nuclei (CCN) are a fraction of atmospheric particles on the surface
332 of which water vapor will condense at a given supersaturation. Cloud droplets can then be formed from the CCN. The
333 most important factor that determines whether a particle will act as CCN or not, is its size, followed by its
334 composition¹. The concentration of CCN significantly affects the characteristics and behavior of the formed clouds¹⁰⁴.

335 The concentration of CCN typically varies from 100 cm^{-3} to 10000 cm^{-3} depending on the region (Figure 9), the
336 number concentration of existing particles able to serve as CCN and the supersaturation⁷². Higher CCN concentrations
337 are found over polluted continental areas¹⁰⁶, such as East Asia, Northeastern US and Europe, while the lowest
338 concentrations are over remote marine regions^{2,40}. Typical water vapor supersaturations in the atmosphere vary
339 between 0.01 and 1%¹⁰⁴ which can notably change the above predictions of CCN concentrations.

340 Observations in pristine continental areas suggest high anthropogenic impact due to long-range transport of pollutants
341 and higher than expected CCN concentrations (a few hundred cm^{-3})¹⁰⁴. Biomass burning, especially over large,
342 forested areas such as the Amazon or the sub-Saharan Africa, can also significantly affect CCN levels¹⁰⁷. New particle
343 formation inside biomass burning plumes can further increase the CCN levels over pristine areas¹⁰⁸.

344 **Ice nuclei:** Ice nuclei (IN) are a tiny fraction of atmospheric particles that provide the appropriate surface for the
345 formation of ice crystals at air temperatures between -5°C and -35°C that are higher than the temperatures needed for
346 homogeneous freezing of water (as low as -38°C). Approximately, 1 in 10^5 particles in continental air - can act as IN
347 at temperatures warmer than -30°C ¹⁰⁹.

348 IN include a fraction of dust particles, mainly those consisting of K-feldspar and quartz¹¹⁰. Organic-rich soil dust from
349 agricultural lands¹¹¹, some sea spray¹¹² and marine biological particles¹¹³, terrestrial bioaerosols¹¹⁴, BC containing
350 biomass burning particles¹¹⁵ and volcanic ash are also IN active atmospheric particles.

351 Observations of IN from various environments show IN levels spanning 7 orders of magnitude from 10^{-5} L^{-1} at -5°C
352 to 150 L^{-1} at colder temperatures (-20°C to -30°C). At temperatures less than -30°C IN concentrations hardly reach
353 10^2 L^{-1} ¹¹⁶. In the Arctic IN levels vary by 5 orders of magnitude with higher concentrations during summer¹¹⁷. The
354 largest seasonal variability was observed for IN activating at warmer temperatures, with concentrations that increase
355 drastically when ice is melting. These IN are potentially associated with dust and terrestrial bioaerosol particles emitted
356 from natural sources that are affected by climate warming¹¹⁷.

357 Global model simulations¹⁰⁵ show large IN spatial variability with the lowest zonal mean levels of the order of 10^5 L^{-1}
358 ¹ near surface over the Arctic and the highest in the mid tropical troposphere 10^2 L^{-1} (Figure 9). The tropical IN are

359 mainly terrestrial bioaerosol while in the high latitudes of the northern hemisphere mid-and high troposphere dust
360 particles are the main IN.

361 *Environmental factors driving aerosol variability*

362 Aerosols present large spatial and temporal variability of up to about 3 orders of magnitude in mass and 5 orders of
363 magnitude in number that are associated with the dependence of their sources and sinks on meteorological conditions
364 and human activities. These environmental factors can explain a number of patterns that appear in aerosol variability
365 across the globe at certain areas.

366 **Seasonal variability:** Factors that drive the seasonal variability of aerosol include wind characteristics and atmospheric
367 mixing, emissions of aerosols and of their precursor organic gases, photochemical intensity, and cloud cover and
368 precipitation. Primary biogenic aerosol emissions and concentrations peak during spring and summer, when vegetation
369 is blooming. Microbial concentrations are usually high in summer and low in winter⁸⁵. In urban areas like Beijing, the
370 highest concentrations of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ are observed in winter due to emissions from heating, lower wind speed,
371 and higher relative humidity, while the lowest concentrations, 2.5 to 5 times lower, occurred in summer due to higher
372 precipitation and mixing¹¹⁸.

373 In the Arctic, aerosol number concentrations show a strong seasonal cycle, with higher concentrations in the
374 accumulation mode during winter and in the Aitken mode during summer due to NPF¹¹⁹. In the boreal region, during
375 cold air outbreaks NPF occurrence increases the nucleation mode particle number; while during summer the elevated
376 terpene emissions oxidize to produce lower volatility organics, which partially counterbalance the NPF suppression
377 induced by sub-tropical air masses rich in pre-existing aerosols reaching the region⁵⁴.

378 **Solar radiation:** High solar activity and temperature enhance biogenic emissions of organics and their oxidation
379 leading to aerosol formation¹²⁰ which in turn affects radiation, cloud formation and climate. High solar activity also
380 enhances aerosol photochemical aging in the atmosphere⁴⁴. Sunny areas with VOC emissions (anthropogenic and
381 biogenic) are characterized by high levels of SOA. Also, the levels of sulfates can peak in such areas (for example in
382 the Eastern Mediterranean)¹²¹.

383 Sunlight is needed for the production of sulfuric acid and the organic vapors that participate in nucleation. So, particle
384 number concentrations tend to increase at areas with higher solar radiation¹²².

385 **Regional climate:** Regional climate affects strongly the aerosol levels since precipitation is their most important
386 removal process and photochemistry and warm temperatures enhance secondary aerosol formation. For example, large
387 variability is seen during the various phases of Monsoons. The pre-monsoon season is characterized by elevated
388 aerosol layers in the free troposphere over India¹²³, which contains large amounts of BC aerosols (as high as 12 µg m⁻³)¹²⁴. During the monsoon season, aerosols are mostly confined to the lower troposphere and are removed during
389 rainfall, however they build up fast after the rain, in particular the absorbing aerosols¹²⁵. The AOD and light extinction
390 by aerosol is lower across India during the active phase and higher during the Monsoon break (dry spell) and during
391 weak Monsoons¹²⁶.

393 **Topography effects:** Topography and small-scale variations in atmospheric circulation (valley breezes, boundary layer
394 height variation) affect aerosol concentrations. Some of the historically most polluted areas in Europe (Po Valley) and
395 the US (Los Angeles) are densely populated urban areas surrounded by mountains and the sea. The coastal areas of
396 these valleys are on average cleaner because they receive cleaner air.

397 Mountain sites (above 1000 m) show very low aerosol number concentrations most of the time. However, when the
398 boundary layer height increases, they can be affected by emissions of cities and villages in the valleys. In these valleys,
399 even at high altitudes there can be significant particle concentrations due to stagnation¹²⁷.

400 **EFFECTS OF VARIATION ON HUMAN HEALTH, CLIMATE CHANGE AND ECOSYSTEMS**

401 In this section we focus on how the large variability in aerosol mass, number, and composition discussed in the
402 previous sections is reflected on their effects on human health, ecosystems, meteorology, and climate, which also
403 present significant regional and temporal patterns.

404 **Human Health:** Aerosols (especially the fine particles) can reach the most sensitive parts of our lungs where they can
405 cause oxidative stress leading after a few days to heart attacks, strokes, lung problems, and in some cases death¹¹. In
406 longer timescales they can lead to lung cancer, cardiopulmonary mortality and also a number of other diseases^{128,129}.
407 These health effects until now have been linked with a high degree of confidence with the mass concentrations of the
408 fine particles (PM_{2.5}) and the different particle components are treated as equally dangerous. However, the capacity
409 of PM to produce damaging oxidative reactions in the human lungs varies with its chemical composition, surface area,
410 and size. There are indications that SOA especially from biomass burning and heavy metals may be inducing a lot
411 more oxidative stress than average¹³⁰. Heavy metals contained in aerosols can be toxic for humans²³. The content of
412 aerosols in heavy metals (e.g. As, Cd, Cr, Ni, Pb, Mn, V, Cu and Zn), which are cancerogenic, can vary upon location,
413 being higher in industrial areas, and upon aerosol size with higher levels of water-soluble metals in fine PM¹³¹.
414 Polyaromatic compounds and the associated black carbon are also considered especially dangerous¹³². The coating
415 of BC by organics increases the corresponding particle toxicity, leading to larger genotoxicity and suppression of the
416 immune system¹³². Better quantification of the spatial variability of these PM components and sources is needed for
417 epidemiological studies that attempt to move beyond PM_{2.5} mass as a health metric.

418 The smallest aerosol particles (UFP with diameter <100 nm, PM_{0.1}) can penetrate deeper in the human body reaching
419 pulmonary alveoli, blood and essentially all organs, including the brain and are considered especially harmful for
420 human health. PM_{0.1} exposure predisposes individuals to ischemic cardiovascular disease and hypertension and has
421 been linked to diabetes and cancer¹³³. However, the epidemiological studies trying to link UFP number and health
422 have been inconclusive¹³⁴. UFPs are considered an emerging pollutant by the European Union and efforts to use other
423 metrics for their health effects (e.g., mass or surface) are in progress¹³⁵.

424 **Meteorology:** While aerosol climate interactions remain largely uncertain, there is consensus that by scattering and
425 absorbing radiation and acting as cloud condensation or ice nuclei, particles cool the atmosphere, increase diffuse light
426 fraction, affect atmospheric stability and humidity, and thereby meteorology and large-scale circulation^{121,136,137}. In
427 addition, aerosols emitted by fires contribute to fire-induced changes in humidity, lightning, diffuse light, precipitation
428 and leaf area index, leading to changes in fire emissions^{138,139} and contribute to fasten regional climate change¹⁴⁰.

429 Scattering and absorption of solar radiation by aerosols within the boundary layer (BL) reduce heat flux, weaken
430 turbulence, increase moisture, enhance aerosol hygroscopic growth, scattering of light, and potential secondary aerosol
431 formation by aqueous phase reactions. These processes can also increase atmospheric stability by reducing surface
432 temperature while absorbing radiation at higher altitudes, favoring further accumulation of aerosols in the BL, which
433 then interact with radiation leading to a positive feedback between aerosols and BL height that is important during
434 high pollution events¹³⁶. Aerosols can also suppress warm rain, increase low-mid troposphere humidity and strengthen
435 entrainment, affecting large scale tropical circulation¹³⁷.

436 **Climate and related uncertainties:** Aerosols can affect Earth's energy balance through both negative (cooling) and
437 positive (warming) radiative effects, depending on their composition and interactions with solar radiation and clouds.
438 Moreover, due to the high spatial variability of aerosols, their impact on the global energy balance is heterogeneous,
439 inducing regional climate change patterns close and downwind of their sources.

440 Scattering of solar radiation by aerosols is known to partially regionally counterbalance the warming effect caused by
441 greenhouse gases. As clean air policies are implemented around the globe, the scattering aerosol effect is weakened
442 (aerosol brightening) and the masking of the climate warming induced by greenhouse gases is reduced, resulting in
443 faster regional warming at different regions of the globe during different periods¹²¹. The mixing of aerosol components
444 is important for the overall properties of an aerosol. BC is a short-lived climate forcer with a lifetime of a few days, it
445 is absorbing radiation and re-emitting it, leading to warming of the atmospheric layers where BC is present. Thus, BC
446 acts synergistically with greenhouse gases to warm climate and, because of its short lifetime and presence in
447 atmospheric layers BC, also alters atmospheric stability and cloud optical and precipitation properties¹⁴¹. When BC is
448 mixed/ coated by scattering aerosol components, its absorption properties may be enhanced and thereby its climate
449 warming efficacy. This effect depends on the available aerosol components which vary among locations and time. At

450 a Mediterranean site an average enhancement of approximately a factor of two has been found for the absorption at
451 370 and 880 nm¹⁴².

452 Clouds' sensitivity to aerosol number concentration depends on meteorological conditions and particularly the updraft
453 velocity¹⁴³. Therefore, it is difficult to establish relationships between aerosols, clouds and precipitation¹⁴⁴. Aerosols
454 acting as CCN lead to warm clouds, while IN contribute to mixed phase clouds¹⁴⁵. During their lifecycle in the
455 atmosphere, depending on environmental conditions, aerosols can be converted from IN to CCN or develop to giant
456 CCN as is the case of dust¹⁴⁶. Considering that mixed phase clouds are more transparent to solar radiation than
457 liquid/warm clouds, changes of IN to CCN can lead to positive or negative climate feedbacks, depending on the
458 concentration of the IN in the clouds and its dependence on temperature¹⁴⁶. Vergara-Temprado et al.¹⁴⁷ have shown
459 that the very-low concentration of IN in the Southern Ocean strongly suppresses cloud droplet freezing, reduces
460 precipitation, and enhances cloud reflectivity.

461 **Effects on ecosystems:** Aerosol pollution increases the fraction of diffuse radiation by scattering light and therefore
462 the efficiency of photosynthesis over land¹⁴⁸. On the contrary, adsorption of aerosols onto the leaves reduces the
463 penetrating light and blocks the opening of stomata causing negative effects to the plants¹⁴⁹. Furthermore, aerosols
464 contain elements, like P, N, Fe and Cu, that are needed for the formation of aminoacids, nucleic acids and proteins
465 that are the building blocks of life. Biomass production is required to sustain life on Earth and is controlled by the
466 photosynthetic activity of the terrestrial and marine ecosystems¹⁵⁰. This in turn is often limited by the availability of
467 one or more trace elements¹⁵¹. Therefore, through atmospheric deposition of these elements, aerosols affect
468 ecosystems growth and functioning¹⁵². Atmospheric aerosol may also contain toxic forms or toxic levels of trace
469 elements¹⁵³. The variability of atmospheric aerosol levels and chemical composition as well as their chemical aging
470 during atmospheric transport leading to more soluble forms of trace elements under atmospheric acidity conditions¹⁵⁴.
471 This in turn affects atmospheric deposition fluxes of nutrients and their relative abundance and shows large
472 spatiotemporal variability of more than 5 orders of magnitude between land and the remote ocean¹⁵⁵. The impact of
473 atmospheric deposition of N, Fe and P (Fig. 10a-c) on the global marine productivity was estimated was found to
474 increase by 20% regional productivity in oligotrophic areas of the Northern Hemisphere (Figure 10) ¹⁵⁶.

475 **OUTLOOK**

476 The high spatial and temporal variability of aerosols is a major obstacle in our efforts to improve air quality and to
477 reduce the uncertainty of future climate change projections. Accurate measurements of particle mass, number, size
478 distribution, composition and properties are technically possible but are expensive. This limits the number of
479 measurement sites both in urban areas and the background. There are significant gaps in the developing world, over
480 the oceans, and aloft.

481 Limited information about aerosol number concentrations exists mostly from field campaigns of limited duration. The
482 ACTRIS network in Europe has provided valuable information about variability in the continental scale. Additional
483 efforts are starting from the US ASCENT network. There is a clear need for additional particle number distribution
484 monitoring both in urban areas but also in a variety of underrepresented areas in the southern hemisphere or remote
485 marine areas worldwide. Measurements of CCN and IN remain challenging and are clearly lacking.

486 Remote sensing using satellites is helping fill the observation gap at the global and regional scales and there is progress
487 in the urban scale. Combing the satellite data with artificial intelligence techniques and chemistry-transport modeling
488 can provide additional insights about particle composition and sources at all scales.

489 The development of low-cost PM mass sensors is also helping map better the mass concentration of especially fine
490 PM in urban areas, but also in areas where no other measurements exist. There is a clear need for the scientific
491 community to intensify its efforts for the development of low-cost sensors for particle number and composition and
492 also to quantify the uncertainty of these measurements. Furthermore, since aerosols can travel great distances,
493 international collaboration is crucial to successfully reduce the exposure of civilians to high aerosol concentrations.

494 The improvement of modeling tools used for the assessment of the effects of aerosols on human health, climate and
495 ecosystems is also necessary. Areas of priority include the simulations of aerosols (mass, number distribution and
496 composition at high spatial resolution in cities, the description of aerosol-cloud interactions in climate models, and
497 the aerosol-ecosystem interactions.

498 *Lead contact*

499 Further information and requests for resources and reagents should be directed to and will be fulfilled by the lead
500 contact, Spyros N. Pandis (spyros@chemeng.upatras.gr)

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509 **AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS**

510 Conceptualization, S.E.I.M, M.K., and S.N.P.; methodology, E.S., K.S., and S.M.; writing-review & editing, S.E.I.M., A.A.,
511 E.S., K.S., S.M., M.K., and S.N.P.; supervision, S.E.I.M, and S.N.P

512 **DECLARATION OF INTERESTS**

513 The authors declare no competing interests.

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515 **FIGURE (AND SCHEME) TITLES AND LEGENDS**

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Figure 1. The schematic illustrates of the major sources, atmospheric processes and size distributions of atmospheric aerosol and two examples of spatial distribution, one over a larger region (Europe) and one over an urban area (Athens, Greece).

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Figure 2. Average predicted PM_{2.5} concentrations (μg m⁻³) from various local sources and long-range transport (sources outside the area) during summer and winter of 2019 in Athens predicted by PMCAMx. PM long range transport is relatively uniform while the dominant local sources (industry, road transport, shipping, biomass burning) have significant spatial gradients.

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Figure 3: Spatial variations of $PM_{2.5}$ concentrations originating from different emission sources as simulated by the PMCAMx-PSAT model.

(a) - (d) July 2019 for Europe

(e) - (h) July 2010 for US.

Adapted from Skylakou et al.⁶⁶ and Skylakou et al.⁶⁷.

537 **Figure 4. Climatological seasonal mean of the AOD at 550 nm from the MAIAC algorithm over the period**
 538 **2000–2021.**
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540 (a) June–July–August

541 (b) December –January–February.

542 The right side of each figure shows the latitudinal average of AOD. Adapted from Di Antonio et al.¹².

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545 **Figure 5. Annual multi-model median near-surface global distribution of fine aerosol**

546 (a) sulfate

547 (b) organic aerosol

548 (c) black carbon

549 (d) dust

550 (e) sea salt in $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$

551 Adapted from Fanourgakis et al.⁷².

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Figure 6. Vertical profiles of aerosol mass concentrations from 13 flights in the Amazon tropical region.

- (a) organics
- (b) nitrate
- (c) sulfate
- (d) ammonium
- (e) BC
- (f) total aerosol

Adapted from Schultz et al.⁷⁷.

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570 **Figure 7. Ground level spatial distributions of total particle number concentration and fine PM levels over**
 571 **Europe during July 2019 predicted by PMCAMx-UF and PMCAMx respectively.**

572 (a) total particle number concentration

573 (b) fine particle PM levels

574 The high number concentrations are due to nucleation and combustion sources. The high mass areas are due to
 575 biomass burning and secondary aerosol production.

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581 **Figure 8. Global distribution of annual multi-model median concentrations of N_3 , N_{50} and cloud condensation**
582 **nuclei at 0.2% supersaturation, $\text{CCN}_{0.2}$ (cm^{-3}) for 2011.**
583 (a) N_3
584 (b) N_{50}
585 (c) cloud condensation nuclei at 0.2% supersaturation, $\text{CCN}_{0.2}$ (cm^{-3})
586 Adapted from Fanourgakis et al.⁷².
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 590 **Figure 9. Predicted multi-year mean IN levels derived from dust, marine primary organic aerosol and PBAP.**
 591 (a) at a pressure level of 600 hPa for an activation temperature of -20°C .
 592 (b) at zonal mean from surface to 300 hPa pressure level at ambient temperature.
 593 Adapted from Chatziparaschos et al.¹⁰⁵.
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 597 **Figure 10. Annual mean deposition fluxes of soluble nitrogen (DN), soluble iron (DFe) and soluble phosphorus (DP) over the ocean (top panels) and annual mean nitrogen fixation and primary production (bottom panels) as calculated using an ocean-biogeochemistry model as part of the EC-Earth Earth system model.**
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 600 Figure adapted from Myriokefalitakis et al.¹⁵⁶.

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604 **TABLES**

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Table 1: Approximate emission rates of total PM emitted and its precursors

Source	Emission Rate (Tg y ⁻¹)
<i>Natural primary</i>	
Soil dust	1000 – 3000
Sea salt	1000 – 6000
Wildfires	20 – 35
Primary biogenic aerosols (bacteria)	0.04 – 1.8
Primary biogenic aerosols (spores)	30
Primary biogenic aerosols (pollen)	47 - 84
<i>Natural precursors of secondary aerosol</i>	
Dimethyl sulfide (DMS)	20 – 40 ^a
Volcanic SO ₂	6 – 20 ^a
Biogenic VOCs	40 – 400
<i>Anthropogenic primary</i>	
Black carbon (BC)	40 – 130
Organic carbon (OC)	50 – 90
Biomass burning	6 – 10
Industrial dust	20 – 30
<i>Anthropogenic precursors of secondary aerosol</i>	
SO ₂	70 – 90 ^a
NO _x	30 – 40 ^b
NH ₃	20 – 50 ^b
Volatile organic compounds (VOCs)	100 – 560 ^c

606 Table is adapted from Boucher²⁶, Primary biogenic aerosol pollen is adapted from Hoose et al.²⁷ and Jacobson et
607 al.²⁸

608 ^a Tg S yr⁻¹

609 ^b Tg N yr⁻¹

610 ^c Tg C yr⁻¹

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